

Netizen's Angry Emotions Expression in Comments on the Facebook Account "Humas Polda Jatim" (Psycholinguistics Approach)

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ABSTRACT : Social media is a place for netizens to express their emotions of anger. This study aims to describe the forms and causes of netizen's angry expressions in comments on posts on the East Java Regional Police Public Relations Facebook account. This research includes qualitative descriptive research. The research data is in the form of diction and figure of speech that contain angry emotions. The source of this research data is the East Java Regional Police Public Relations (Humas Polda Jatim) Facebook account post on September 4, 2022. Data collection uses free engagement speaking technique, screenshot technique, and note-taking technique. Data analysis uses referential and pragmatic equivalent methods. The results of this study indicate that netizen's angry emotions are expressed in words, phrases, sentences, and 10 kinds of figure of speech that contain negative meanings or something they hate, have harsh connotations, show annoyance and distrust, demean the police, swear, pray for bad, and satirize smooth to coarse. In this study, it was also found that there were two factors that caused netizens to experience angry emotions, namely (a) cases that occurred among the internal police and (b) netizen's own experiences when dealing with PJR members on the toll road.

KEYWORDS –angry, emotion, netizen, police, psycholinguistics

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Humans need language in everyday life. Everyone used language as a tool to communicate and interact with other people (Susanthi, 2022). Through communication, one can convey what she or he wants to convey or mean to someone, such as expressing an idea or opinion, sharing information, asking something, suggesting, etc. (Agustian, 2022). In addition, language is also used by humans to express their feelings. Hymes suggests that language has seven functions, one of which is the expressive or emotive function (Aslinda & Syafyahya, 2010:91). In this case, language is not only for conveying information but also serves as a tool for expressing feelings or emotions. Furthermore, Suharti et al. (2021:165) also argues that the language that processes in humans is reflected in the condition of his soul. Therefore, through language, the listener can predict the speaker's psychological condition, whether the speaker is sad, angry, happy, or in other circumstances.

The function of language as a tool for expressing emotions can easily be found on social media. Social media is media in the form of sites and applications that involve internet-based technology that encourages and allows users to connect with anyone, both close people and strangers who were previously unknown (Triastuti et al., 2017:16). Social media users are referred to as netizens. Through social media, netizens can communicate with each other virtually, share content, provide comments, and so on. With the comments feature, social media is not only useful as a means of communication, but also used as a place to express emotions. One example is

netizen comments in account posts Humas Polda Jatim (2022) which was uploaded on September 4, 2022 on Facebook.

The post contains clarification from the police regarding the virality of videos that contain false information regarding members of the police. Previously, it was reported that social media users were shocked by a viral video that lasted 2 minutes and 20 seconds. In the video, there is a man wearing glasses getting out of a sports car, then approaching a patrol car and mentioning that a member of the Highway Patrol (PJR) make extortion by asking a pickup driver for Rp 500,000. The incident occurred on the Lebani Gresik Toll Road, East Java on September 3, 2022 (Ansyari& Faishal, 2022).

Regarding this incident, the East Java regional police made a clarification with the aim of rectifying the untrue information. The clarification was made in the form of a video post uploaded to the East Java Police Public Relations Facebook account. After the clarification video was released, two versions of the news circulated in the community, namely the news version of the police and the news version of men using Pajero Spot car (Tim CekFakta, 2022). As of September 29, 2022, the police clarification video has been viewed 306 thousand times and received more than 4 thousand comments by Facebook users. The contents of the comments from netizens are very diverse. Even though the police have made a clarification video, it turns out that many netizens have given negative comments to the police institution. This comment is an expression of a netizen's expression as well as showing the psychological condition of netizens towards events involving the police institution.

Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting research with the title expressions of anger by netizens in comments on Facebook account posts "Humas Polda Jatim". The phenomenon under study is related to language and a person's psychological condition. Therefore, this study uses psycholinguistics approach.

1.2 Relevant Researches

Relevant research has been carried out by several parties. First, Nurfadila & Andari (2019) examines the emotional expressions of fear of the characters in the Bleach manga. In this study, expressions of fear were found in the form of anxiety, nervousness, worry, anxiety, alertness, sadness, horror, phobias, and panic. Second, Erwandari & Khasanah (2020) examine expressions of anger in the comic Crayon Shinchan. In this study, expressions of anger were found in the form of onomatopoeia, particles, and expressions of commands and prohibitions. Subsequent, research conducted by Khotami (2020), Azmiati & Nuryani (2021), and Solihat & Devi (2022). Research from the three has similarities, namely both examine children's emotional expressions. In her research, Khotami (2020) produce findings that the emotional expression of children aged 1-2 years is limited to the phonological aspect. Azmiati & Nuryani (2021) explain the findings that the emotional expression of children aged 1-3 years is in the phonological aspect up to the word level. As for Solihat & Devi (2022) produce findings, namely the expression of early childhood emotions in the form of basic words and affixed words.

After conducting a literature review, the authors found that previous research focused on examining expressive expressions in children, characters in comics or illustrated stories, and characters in animated films. As far as the author knows, research that examines the expressive expressions spoken by netizens in the comments column on Facebook, especially on police social media accounts, has never been investigated.

1.3. Purpose of the Study

The formulation in this research is how netizens express angry emotions in comments on the Facebook account post "Humas Polda Jatim" and what are the causative factors? With the formulation of the problem, it can be explained that the purpose of this study is to describe the use of language in expressing angry emotions in comments on the Facebook account post "Humas Polda Jatim" and also to describe the causative factors.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Psycholinguistics

The birth of the study of psycholinguistics began in a quarter of a century ago. Psychologists consider that research on psychophysiology and neurophysiology can be carried out using a language approach. Therefore, these experts began to try to do research by mixing psychology and language. As a result, in the following period, a new science emerged, namely psycholinguistics.

Psycholinguistics is an interdisciplinary study between linguistics and psychology. In other words, it can be understood that psycholinguistics is the study of language in relation to psychological conditions. Yendra (2018:296) said that psycholinguistics is the study of psychological and neurobiological factors that enable humans to acquire, use, and understand language. The main study in psycholinguistic research is to explore something that happens when someone uses or receives language. Psycholinguistics examines the psychological and neurobiological factors that enable people to learn, use, and understand language (Diwyarthi et al., 2022:66).

2.2 Angry Emotions

Language is not only limited as a means of communication, but also has other functions such as expressive or emotive functions (Jakobson in Wijana, 2018). Based on this, it can be understood that language activity indirectly is also an activity of expressing emotions. Emotions are a condition in which a person is influenced by certain situations, tends to occur in relation to behavior that leads or avoids something, accompanied by physical expressions, so that other people know that the person is experiencing emotions (Fitri & Adelya, 2017; Fitriyah, 2018; Saleh, 2018:107–108). The physical expression has various forms. Forms of physical expression can be in the form of anger, sadness, joy, love, hate, and so on.

Furthermore, Widodo (2016:34–35) suggests that emotion is a reaction or response to internal and external stimuli from a person. For example, sad emotions encourage someone to cry, happy emotions encourage someone to smile, and so on. In addition to causing a response, the emergence of emotions also has a cause (Yanizon & Sesriani, 2019). There are factors that cause someone to experience sad emotions, for example due to having an accident, failing to reach a goal, or something else they don't like. Likewise, a person experiencing happy emotions has a causal factor, for example because he gets a gift or praise, the realization of his goals, or other things he likes.

According to Rozali, human emotions are generally divided into two kinds, namely positive emotions and negative emotions (Candra et al., 2017:92). Positive emotions or pleasant emotions are emotions that cause positive feelings in people who experience them, such as love, affection, joy, admiration, and so on. Negative emotions or unpleasant emotions are emotions that cause negative feelings in those who experience them, such as sadness, anger, hate, and fear.

Angry emotion is the emotion that most often appears in everyday speech. It's because of people generally identify the term emotion with anger (Al-Firdaus, 2011:74). Angry emotion is a type of emotion that makes people go against the source of frustration (Mahmud in Sobur, 2016:354). Angry emotion is also a signal that appears in a person to defend himself from harassment and deprivation of individual rights (Falentina & Yulianti, 2012). Nasirudin (2017) argues that anger becomes a dominant feeling in behavior, knowledge, and physically when a person makes a conscious choice to act in order to directly stop threats that come from outside. Anger is a behavior pattern designed to warn bullies to stop threatening behavior.

2.3 Forms of Angry Emotions

A person who is experiencing the emotion of anger is manifested in several forms. Since this research is focused on psycholinguistics approach, the forms of angry emotions that are discussed and analyzed in this study are words, phrases, clauses, sentences, and figure of speech.

A word is a unit of language that can stand alone, can be a single morpheme or can be joined with other bound morphemes (Sitorus, 2019:153). In simple terms, words can be interpreted as a means to realize the unity of one's feelings and thoughts when speaking. Phrases are combinations of two or more words that are non-

predicative; can also be interpreted as a unit consisting of two or more words, each of which retains the basic meaning of the word (Yendra, 2018:165). A clause is a syntactic unit in the form of a sequence of words with a predicative construction; consists of several words or phrases that function as subjects and predicates (Shalima, 2018:78). Clauses are linguistic elements that are at a smaller level than sentences and are at a larger level than phrases and contain subject and predicate elements (Yendra, 2018:172). Sentence is the largest grammatical unit that contains a predicate and expresses a thought; in spoken form, the sentence is marked with the final intonation; in written form, sentences begin with a capital letter and end with punctuation (Moeliono et al., 2017:407).

Figure of speech is a way of expressing thoughts through language in a unique way so that it shows the soul and personality of the user of that language (Keraf, 2009:113). According to him, figure of speech based on the direct or indirect meaning is directly divided into two groups, namely (1) rhetorical language style and (2) figurative language style. Rhetorical language style is a style of language that is solely a deviation from ordinary constructions to achieve certain effects. The types of rhetorical language styles are (a) alliteration, (b) asonance, (c) anastrophe, (d) apophasis, (e) apostrophe, (f) asyndeton, (g) polysyndeton, (h) chiasmus, (i) ellipsis, (j) euphemism, (k) litotes, (l) proteron hysteron, (m) pleonasm or tautology, (n) periphrasis, (o) prolepsis, (p) erotesis, (q) sylepsis or zeugma, (r) correction, (s) hyperbole, (t) paradox, and (u) oxymoron. Figurative language style is a style of language that experiences further deviations in meaning and is formed based on comparisons or similarities. The types of figurative language styles are (a) simile, (b) metaphor, (c) allegory, parable, fable, (d) personification, (e) allusion, (f) eponym, (g) epithet, (h) synecdoche, (i) metonymy, (j) antonomasia, (k) hypallage, (l) irony, cynicism, sarcasm, (m) inuendo, (n) satire, (o) antiphrasis, and (p) paronomasia.

III. METHOD OF RESEARCH

This research is included in the type of qualitative research using descriptive methods. Suyitno (2018:6) argues that qualitative research is research that stems from an inductive mindset and is based on participatory objective observation of a social phenomenon. Descriptive method is used because this research aims to explain and describe the use of language by netizens as a means to express angry emotions on Facebook. The data of this study are in the form of diction and figure of speech that contain expressions of angry emotions. The source of the data in this research is the comments made by netizens in the posts Humas Polda Jatim (2022) on Facebook. From the search results, the majority of netizens' comments were expressions of angry emotions. Since the data is homogeneous, the researcher used a random sampling technique and selected 60 comments from netizens.

The data collection stage used the free-involved viewing technique, the screenshot technique, and the note-taking technique. The first technique was used because the researcher only observes into comments submitted by netizens on Facebook without engaging in conversations with netizens. Furthermore, researchers took screenshots of netizen comments. Then, the researcher recorded the comments in text form and classified them according to the purpose of this study.

After the data is collected, the next step is data analysis. The data analysis method used in this study is the referential equivalent method and the pragmatic equivalent method. Zaim (2014:99-101) explains that the determining tool in the referential equivalent method is the referent or reality designated by that language, while the determining tool in the pragmatic equivalent method is the speech partner. The referential equivalent method is used in this study to determine the referents of the emotional expressions conveyed by netizens. Meanwhile, the pragmatic equivalent method is used in this study to determine the factors that cause netizens to comment using emotional expressions.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The post on the East Java Regional Police Public Relations (Humas Polda Jatim) Facebook account on September 4, 2022 was a post from the police which aimed to clarify news circulating in the community. The post is in the form of a video accompanied by an explanatory text that members of the East Java Regional Police PJR do not commit extortion.

The post received many responses from netizens. As many as 2.8 thousand netizens responded with laughing emojis, 2000 netizens responded with like emojis, 74 netizens gave shocked emojis, 30 netizens gave heart emojis, 23 netizens gave angry emojis, 12 netizens gave sad emojis, and 6 netizens gave emojis care. The post also received many comments from netizens. As of September 29, 2022, the post has received more than 4000 comments in written language. The use of language as an expression of netizen's angry emotions is expressed in the form of words, phrases, sentences, and figure of speech. This research also found the causes of netizens experiencing angry emotions. Both of these are described as follows.

4.1 Expressions of Angry Emotions

The emotions of netizens in the comments on the East Java Police Public Relations Facebook account posts are expressed in the form of words, phrases, sentences, and figure of speech. The four forms of language are described below.

4.1.1 Word

The netizen's angry emotions were first manifested in words. Word is language unit that can stand alone, can be a single morpheme or can be joined with other bound morphemes (Sitorus, 2019:153). Words used to express angry emotions are words that have a negative meaning or something that is hated. An example of finding data on angry expressions of netizens in the form of words is as follows.

[Data 1]

In data 1 above, netizen's comment that show angry emotions known from the use of the word 'berbohong' (lying). That word has the meaning of 'saying something that is not true'. The word has a negative meaning or something people hate. That's because people generally hate being lied to by others.

In addition to the examples above, the following is a list of netizen's angry emotional expressions in the form of words found in this study.

Glossary (Indonesian)	Meaning
Bohong, berbohong	lie, lying
kebohongan	the lie
alibi	alibi
pungli	extortion
mustahil	impossible
rendah	low
kezaliman	tyranny

4.1.2 Phrase

The second netizen's angry emotion is manifested in the form of a phrase. Phrase is combinations of two or more words that are non-predicative; can also be interpreted as a unit consisting of two or more words, each

of which retains the basic meaning of the word (Yendra, 2018:165). The phrases used to express angry emotions are in the form of phrases that have a negative meaning, belittle certain parties, swear, have harsh connotations, and show distrust of the police. An example of finding data on netizen's angry expressions in the form of phrases is as follows.

[Data 2]

*In my opinion, this institution is a **burden on the state**, it is very dilapidated, it has made mistakes but is looking for justification.*

In data 2 above, the comments of netizens showing angry emotions are known from the use of the phrase 'beban negara' (burden on the state). That phrase means 'something heavy that must be borne by the state'. Thus, it can be understood that the intention of the netizen's comments is that the police agency is considered an agency that burdens the state. This phrase has a negative meaning and seems to demean the police.

In addition to the data above, the following is a list of netizen's angry emotion expressions in the form of phrases found in this study.

List of Phrases (Indonesian and Regional Language)	Meaning
Gak percoyo, ra percoyo, tidak percaya	Don't believe
beban negara	burden on the state
drama maneh iki	this drama again
drama lagi	drama again
tidak punya telinga dan mata ya	don't have ears and eyes huh?
banyak oknum	many persons
mainkan pasal-pasal	play chapters
asem ane	fuck it
kebobrokan oknum-oknum polisi	the depravity of the police officers
ngedabrus tok	Always bullshit
tukang palak rakyat	people's handyman
tukang tipu	fraudster
mental pemalak	lazy mentality

4.1.3 Sentence

The third netizen's angry emotion is manifested in the form of a sentence. Sentence is the largest grammatical unit that contains a predicate and expresses a thought; in spoken form, the sentence is marked with the final intonation; in written form, sentences begin with a capital letter and end with punctuation (Moeliono et al., 2017:407). Sentences used to express angry emotions are in the form of sentences containing prayers for evil and expressions of annoyance towards the police. An example of finding data on angry expressions of netizens in the form of sentences is as follows.

[Data 3]

It looks like he's done it before, to be honest, it's impossible to run away. That's it, best regards.

In data 3 above, comments from netizens showing angry emotions are known from the use of the sentence 'ketoro tau melakukan, lek jujur gak mungkin lari' (It looks like he's done it before, to be honest, it's impossible to run away). The netizen's comments mean that the police were found to have committed extortion because he was running while being recorded by a man driving a Pajero Spot car. The netizen also said that if the police were honest, he would definitely not run away and would explain everything at the crime scene.

In addition to the data above, the following is a list of netizen's angry emotion expressions in the form of sentences found in this study.

List of Sentences (Indonesian and Regional Language)	Meaning
mau ditutupi lagi kesalahan sahabatnya	Want to cover up his friend's mistakes again.
ketoro tau melakukan, lek jujur gak mungkin lari	It lookslike he's done it before, to be honest, it's impossible to run away. That's it, best regards.
semoga tuhan membalas yang memutar balik cerita ini paling males berurusan sama polisi karena ujung-ujungnya duit	May god reward the person who twisted this story most lazy to deal with the police because in the end asked for money

4.1.4 Figure of Speech

The fourth netizen's angry emotion is manifested in the form of figure of speech. Figure of speech is a way of expressing thoughts through language in a unique way so that it shows the soul and personality of the language user (Keraf, 2009:113). Figure of speech used to express angry emotions by netizens consist of allusion, ellipsis, hyperbole, irony, cynicism, sarcasm, litotes, paradox, erotesis, and simile. These are explained as follows.

Figure of speech Type	Data (Indonesian and Regional Language)	Meaning
Allusion	Seorang jenderal bintang dua membunuh ajudan sendiri aja direkayasa	A two star general killing his own adjutant just engineered
	Sekelas Brigadir J saja dibuat berita palsu kasusnya	Just in the same class as Brigadier J, the case was made up of fake news
	dasar generasi sambo	the basis of sambo generation
	mudah-mudahan bukan sambo kecil	hopefully not a little sambo
	iki podo ae, kelompok sambo juga	It's the same thing, the sambo group too
	Dasar otak sambo	Basic sambo brain
	sambo kesekian kalinya	sambo for the umpteenth time
Ellipsis	Kualitas Security BCA ternyata lebih baik ya daripada institusi ini ini ... ehem.	The quality of BCA security guards is apparently better than this institution... ahem.
Hyperbole	Sejuta alasanmu pak pak...	A million reasons for you, sir...
Irony	saya lebih percaya sama supir pick up	I trust the pick-up driver more
	Subhanallah pak, luar biasa kinerja institusi ini... Tapi jujur dari lubuk hati yang paling dalam... Saya kok gak yakin!!!	Unbelievable sir, the performance of this institution is extraordinary. But, to be honest from the bottom of my heart, I'm not sure!!!
	Ya percaya aja, mau bagaimanapun tetap polisi yang mengatur cerita	Yes, just believe it, no matter what, it's still the police who arrange the story
Cynicism	ucapanmu sungguh indah, wahai yang mengunggah tak sesuai video asli	your words are really beautiful, O those who uploaded not according to the original video
	lanjutkan kepandaianmu pak	keep going sir
	sebaik apapun skema cerita yang tuan-tuan berikan pada masyarakat, itu tidak akan bisa mengubah citra buruk tuan-tuan sekalian	no matter how good the story scheme that you present to the public, it will not be able to change the bad image of you gentlemen
	Modus = modal dusta, mereka orang-orang pilihan dan cerdas untuk membuat modus-modus baru.	Modus = lying capital, they are chosen and intelligent people to make new modes.

Sarcasm	Kari nglakoni penggaweane cik gobloke, sing drama, sing taek asu... Cok	Just do the job, so stupid, the drama, the dog shit, fuck
Litotes	PJR tidak ada gunanya, hanya menyengsarakan sopir	PJR is useless, it only makes the driver miserable
	Polisi itu baik, ramah, sopan, dan mengayomi masyarakat, tapi itu hanya berlaku di depan kamera saja	The police are kind, friendly, polite and protect the community, but that only applies in front of the camera
Paradox	Polisi yang baik itu cuma sedikit, yang tidak baik banyak	The good police are few, the bad are many
	Polisi baik sekarang malah jadi oknum, sisanya polisi tidak baik	The good police are now the bad guys. The rest, the cops are no good
	Simbolnya objektif dipercaya tapi yang komentar gak ada yang percaya perkataan di atas	The symbol is objective, trusted, but no one who comments believes the words above
Erotesis	Yang dipermasalahkan adalah minta uang 500 itu buat apa?	The problem is what are you asking for the 500 for?
	Kenapa bapak yang bersangkutan main kabur?	Why did the father in question run away?
	Anda polisi, kenapa tidak bersedia menjelaskan waktu di lokasi?	You're a policeman, why aren't you willing to explain the time at the location?
	kalau gak salah, ngapain lari?	if I'm not mistaken, why run away?
	kalau dia benar, kenapa harus takut anggota anda pak?	if he's right, why should you be afraid of your members, sir?
	kalau gak salah ngapain kabur?	if i'm not mistaken, why run away?
	masih percaya kalian sama sambo?	do you still believe in Sambo?
Simile	gak ada bedanya kalian sama mantan, sama-sama buat dendam kesumat	It's no different between you and your ex, both of you are making grudges
	Jangan cari pembenaran seolah-olah kami, rakyat ini yang salah terus	Don't look for justification, as if we, the people are always wrong

Allusion

Allusion is a figure of speech that suggests similarities between people, places, or events (Keraf, 2009:141). Netizens express angry emotions by using allusions with the aim that readers or other people understand that the factors causing netizen's anger have similarities to past events. Thus, it can be said that the thing that causes netizens to be angry is not just one thing but more than that that comes from the past. An example of finding data on angry emotion expressions by netizens in the form of allusions is as follows.

[Data 4]

Beng Beng
lis lis kowe q nk kon gae alibi opo pembelaan kui jian joss ora tau ono polisi indonesia mau mengakui kesalahane karo masyarakat urung tumon nk tentara ees ono dasar generasi sambo.

*Police, if you make an alibi or defense, it's very extraordinary, the Indonesian police have never admitted their mistakes to the public, they have never been found. If the army, already there. **The basis of Sambo generation.***

In data 4 above, netizens commented using allusions. This can be seen from the use of the phrase 'dasar generasi Sambo' (the basic of Sambo generation). Netizens tried to equate the alleged extortion incident as if it had something in common with the case of Ferdy Sambo who killed Brigadier Josua. The Ferdy Sambo case has tarnished the good name of the police institution. This case occurred several months earlier. The case of alleged extortion by PJR members at the Lebani Gresik Toll Road has also tarnished the good name of the police institution. This happened several months after the Ferdy Sambo case.

Ellipsis

Ellipsis is a figure of speech that takes the form of eliminating an element of a sentence which can easily be interpreted by the reader or listener himself (Keraf, 2009:132). An example of finding data on angry emotion expressions by netizens in the form of ellipsis is as follows.

[Data 5]

*The quality of BCA security guards is actually better than **this institution...***
*NB: **censored** (because if it's not censored, it's subject to the ITE Law)*

In data 5 above, netizens comment using ellipsis. This can be seen from the omission of certain parts of the sentence and the addition of the word 'disensor' (censored). Even though that part of the sentence was omitted, other netizens can still easily interpret for themselves that the omitted part of the sentence is 'the police'. This is inseparable from the previous social context, where there was a trending topic on Twitter stating that the quality of BCA security guards is better than the police.

Hyperbole

Hyperbole is a figure of speech that exaggerates a fact (Keraf, 2009:135). An example of finding data on netizen's angry expressions in the form of hyperbole is as follows.

[Data 6]

*You have **a million reasons**, sir. If there is no mistake acting outside the rules, why should run away. Can be explained there. If you dare, please confirm openly in a neutral place with the driver who is being ticketed, without any intervention to the driver who is said to have violated it. Not at the police station. Neutral open space, can be witnessed by many parties. Don't always feel self-righteous, win alone, and society is always the target.*

In data 6 above, netizens provide comments using the phrase 'sejuta alasan' (a million reasons). The netizen's comments mean that the police have made a million reasons to be judged correct by the public. That is, the East Java Regional Police Public Relations post is considered a collection of reasons made with the aim of defending the police who are suspected of committing extortion at the Lebani Gresik Toll Road. The phrase 'a million reasons' is hyperbole because it exaggerates a fact.

Irony, Cynicism, and Sarcasm

Irony, cynicism, and sarcasm are three types of figure of speech that aim to satirize or ridicule certain parties. Although they have similarities, those have fundamental differences (Keraf, 2009:143). Irony is a figure of speech that aims to satirize someone in a subtle way, namely by stating something that is not the same as reality. Cynicism is a figure of speech that aims to satirize someone; in the form of doubt containing ridicule of sincerity and heartfelt writing. Cynicism is cruder than irony. Meanwhile, sarcasm is a figure of speech that aims to satirize someone in a way that is even more rude than irony and cynicism. This figure of speech feels very hurtful and unpleasant to hear. In general, this figure of speech is in the form of swear words. An example of finding data on netizen's angry emotion expressions in the form of irony, cynicism, and sarcasm is as follows.

[Data 7]

*Wow, your speech are really beautiful, O those who uploaded not according to the original video. It is clear that the original video of the STNK and SIM were detained and not returned, even though they had been given 500,000 rupiah (five hundred thousand rupiah) and if the pick-up driver was wrong, why did the police want to run away? **What a beautiful words you say**(the wrong is justified, the right is wronged).*

[Data 8]

*Every day your image is getting destroyed. **Continue your intelligence, sir.** We have no compassion / respect for your institution anymore. Indonesia is like there are 2 countries: 1. civil society, 2. police. Society can still be blamed even if he is right. The police cannot be blamed even if they are wrong.*

[Data 9]

*In fact, netizens are smarter than this institution. Just doing work is **so stupid**. The drama, the dog shit. Work honestly like that you know sir. Can work or not? **Fuck***

Netizen's comments on data 7 above contain irony. This can be seen from the sentence 'ucapanmu sungguh indah; sungguh indah ucapanmu' (your speech are really beautiful; what a beautiful words you say). In fact, this sentence does not contain praise, but satire at the police who are suspected of having extorted money at the Lebani Gresik Toll Road. The satire is made by way of praise which is not the same as reality.

Netizen's comments on data 8 above contain cynicism. This can be seen from the sentence 'lanjutkan kepandaianmu pak' (continue your intelligence, sir). The sentence actually does not contain appreciation but contains satire to the police. The satire feels harsher than irony because the sentences after and before show netizen's expressions of annoyance with the police.

Meanwhile, netizen's comments on data 9 above contain sarcasm. This can be known from the word 'cik gobloke' which means 'so stupid'. That is, netizens think that the performance of the police is so stupid. The netizen's expressions felt more harsh and hurtful than the two previous figure of speech.

Litotes

Litotes is a figure of speech that reduces a reality with the aim of demeaning (Keraf, 2009:132–133). An example of finding data on netizen's angry expressions in the form of litotes is as follows.

[Data 10]

Nowadays PJR is useless, it only makes the driver miserable. Even if we're right, it's still wrong. I hope you repent quickly, because the law of the hereafter is never wrong, even if it's that small. Remember, life will die, do more good, the world is old.

In the 10 data above, netizens commented using the phrase 'PJR tak ada gunanya, hanya menyengsarakan supir' (PJR is useless, it only makes the driver miserable). This sentence is litotes because it means reducing the fact that PJR has no function at all in society. In fact, PJR has the main task of realizing security, safety, order and smoothness on toll roads. Even though there are people who are suspected of having committed extortion, it does not mean that PJR has no function at all.

Paradox

Paradox is a figure of speech that contains a real contradiction with existing facts (Keraf, 2009:136). An example of finding data on netizen's angry expressions in the form of a paradox is as follows.

[Data 11]

The symbol is objective, trusted, but no one giving comments believes the words above. Pity.

Netizen's comments on data 11 above contain a paradox. At first, the netizen said that the Public Relations Division of the National Police had the slogan 'obyektif dipercaya' (objective, trusted). Then, the netizen contrasted the slogan with the reality he got in the comments on the East Java Regional Police Public Relations post. He found that many comments from netizens did not believe the East Java Police Public Relations post.

Erotesis

Erotesis is a figure of speech in the form of a question sentence that is used for emphasis and the question does not actually need an answer (Keraf, 2009:134). An example of finding data on angry emotion expressions by netizens in the form of erotesis is as follows.

[Data 12]

*It's already been found out, sir. If he's not mistaken, **why did he run away**, and even if the pick-up driver was at fault, **why would he accept the money**. It means that your member is also wrong, wanting to accept bribes. If it's like this, I'm sorry sir, it's already difficult to find the true point.*

In data 12 above, netizen's comment using erotesis. The netizen questioned the actions of the police who ran when the man driving the Pajero Sport car was recorded. He also questioned the reasons for the police wanting to accept money from pickup drivers. In fact, the money is strong evidence of indications of extortion. The netizen's question does not actually require an answer, but the question is a form of misunderstanding with the police who are suspected of committing extortion.

Simile

Simile is a figure of speech that equates something with something else explicitly by using the words: like, the same, as if, as though, and so on (Keraf, 2009:138). An example of finding data on angry expressions of netizens in the form of similes is as follows.

[Data 13]

*O, like this is forcing people to believe in you. Already trusted but betrayed, why. **It's no different between you and my ex-boyfriend.** Both of them make grudges.*

Netizen's comments on data 13 above contain similes. Netizens express their emotions by equating the actions taken by the police, namely PJR members, with the actions of ex-boyfriends. The two parties are considered to have something in common. The similarity is that it has caused resentment or hurt.

4.2 Factors Causing Anger Emotions

The angry emotion experienced by a person does not just happen. This is because the emotion of anger is caused by certain factors experienced by that person. Based on the results of data analysis in this study, netizen's expressions of anger in comments on the Facebook account post "Humas Polda Jatim" are known to be due to two causal factors, namely as follows.

4.2.1 Cases that Occurred within the Internal Police Force

The first factor causing netizens to experience angry emotions is due to cases that occurred within the police internal circle. Netizens expressed their angry emotions by linking the alleged extortion case by PJR on the Lebani Gresik toll road and the case of Ferdy Sambo who killed Nofriansyah Yosua Hutabarat. This can be seen from the following data.

[Data 14]

*Remember the first **Sambo** story during the press conference, there was a shooting incident. After that nothing happened. It turns out that even the authorities in certain situations can also lie.*

In data 14 above, netizens expressed their angry emotions by linking the cases of PJR members and the Ferdy Sambo case. Ferdy Sambo is a high-ranking Indonesian National Police officer who killed his colleague Nofriansyah Yosua Hutabarat. During the first press conference, it was said that there had been an exchange of fire between Sambo and Yosua which resulted in Yosua being shot dead. However, during the next press conference, the story changed.

Because of that, many netizens do not believe in PJR member at the Lebani Gresik Toll Road, who ran while being recorded by a man driving a Pajero Spot car. Netizens consider that the clarification video made by the East Java Regional Police Public Relations is a lie. This is because even cases involving high-ranking police officers can be fabricated, let alone cases involving civil society. Therefore, netizens became angry because they strongly suspected that the PJR member had committed extortion.

4.2.2 The Experience of Netizens Themselves

The second factor that causes netizens to experience angry emotions is because of the netizen's own experience. Netizens tell stories of their own experiences as a driver who passes toll roads every day and deals with PJR. This can be seen from the following data.

[Data 15]

Rofii Setya

Alah mental pemalak wes mendrah dagin di institusi anda, anda bela bagai manapun masyarakat sudah sangat faham dgn hal yg demikian....
Sebagai mantan sopir truk bagi saya hal semacam ini sudah terlalu sering teralami dgn berbagai macam alasan....

Suka Balas 7 minggu

The lazy mentality is ingrained in your institution. You defend it no matter what, people are very aware of this. As a former truck driver, for me this kind of thing has been experienced too many times for various reasons.

In the 15 data above, netizens convey their angry emotions towards the police institution by sharing their experiences. When he was a truck driver, the netizen said that he often experienced extortion by police officers. Therefore, these netizens hate the police and do not believe in the clarification video submitted by the East Java Regional Police Public Relations.

V. CONCLUSION

Social media is a place for netizens to express their emotions of anger. The results of this study indicate that netizen's angry emotions in comments on East Java Regional Police Public Relations (Humas Polda Jatim) Facebook account posts are expressed in words, phrases, sentences, and figure of speech. From the 60 data analyzed, it can be concluded that expressions of angry emotions in the form of words were found in 7 data. Expressions of angry emotions in the form of phrases found in 13 data. Expressions of angry emotions in the form of sentences were found in 4 data. Expressions of angry emotions in the form of figure of speech were found in 10 kinds.

The characteristics of netizen's angry emotions are expressed in language that contains negative meanings or something that is hated, has a rough connotation, shows annoyance and distrust, looks down on the police, swears, wishes bad luck, and insinuates subtly to rudeness. In addition, the cause of netizens experiencing angry emotions is due to two factors. The first factor relates to cases that occurred among internal police, which made netizens distrust the clarification videos from the police and oppose the actions of PJR member on the Lebani Gresik toll road. The second factor relates to the experience of netizens themselves when dealing with PJR member on toll roads.

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